

Coffee pulp compost

A viable organic source of nutrients for Soil and Crops

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Abstract

The principles behind composting are specific enzyme production systems of microbes, which can degrade the complex organic debris into simpler substances that crops can utilize as nutrient sources. Coffee pulp is the major residue during the recovery of parchment coffee beans which is left unutilized. This can be converted into utilizable organic manure without endangering the environment by employing potential microbial agents and earthworms. Farmers of the plain region popularly adopt these technologies to produce organic manures from crop residues for sustainable production. Generally, these technologies are less popularized in hill regions due to a lack of knowledge on the decomposition of coffee pulp waste, available microbial decomposition methods and negligence of the importance of the nutritional value of coffee pulp into nutrient rich manure. Hence, the knowledge of composting coffee pulp waste through various composting technologies is essential for the farmers to recycle the wastes into organic manure, which enriches soil nutrients and utilizing in organic farming.

Introduction

Shevaroy hills, the lungs of Eastern Ghat with an extended area of 382.7sq.km covering 67 tribal villages and 25 hamlets in Yercau, Salem District, Tamil Nadu. The hill is endowed with low temperature prevailing landscapes with intensive cultivation of high value horticultural crops viz., Coffee, Black pepper, Orange, Banana, Anthurium, Gerbera and Hill Vegetables. Crops like paddy, finger millet, maize, onion, banana, coconut, tamarind, mango, wheat, mustard etc., are grown by the tribal farmers, especially in lower elevations of the hills. The farmers of Shevroy hills growing coffee as a major commercial crop under multi-tier cropping system. From coffee about 15,000 tons of coffee pulp waste is produced annually, which is not used effectively, and the large quantity of coffee pulp wastes are dumped in open pits. Coffee pulp wastes require a very long

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period for natural degradation due to their high tannins, polyphenols, chlorogenic acid content.

The production of one ton of clean coffee beans leaves around three tons of fruit pulp and cherry husk as wastes (Karthikeyan and Stephen, 2005). The coffee processing industries are generating large amounts of solid wastes that have the potential for organic manure production. Our Indian farmers were basically organic farmers before introducing inorganic fertilizers and chemical pesticides. Applying synthetic fertilizers for crop nutrient had adverse effects on the environment and human health in the due course period. Now the organic method of cultivating crops with organic inputs like vermicompost, bio compost, enriched manure, etc. is essential to produce residue free crop produces and maintain soil fertility. Currently, consumers demand organic products. To progress in organic farming, eco-friendly technologies like vermicomposting, bio composting are essential to produce organic manure to make it available to the farmers. Effective Microorganisms (EM), a mixed culture of various bacteria, actinomycetes, yeast and fungi, have become essential and safe for composting any residues. Effective microorganisms containing a high diversity of beneficial microorganisms can be employed to compost waste in the diversification of the ecosystem. The EM involved compost has improved the soil's biological activity and supports crop growth (Kassa et al., 2011). The coffee husk and pulp contain more macro and micro nutrients and organic matter and caffeine, tannins, and polyphenols (Franca and Oliveira 2009). The waste has more organic compounds and essential nutrients, which can be utilized by proper composting.

Coffee pulp

Microorganisms for the composting of coffee pulp

Generally, the microorganism can decompose the crop residues fallen on the earth for a longer period. Some of the microorganisms have the potential to decompose the wastes in a short duration if the proper environment is adopted in the selection of methods like pit or heap, correct season by avoiding summer and rainy season, specific microorganism based on the composition of waste, which results faster production of organic manures. Studies indicated that the bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* fungi, *Aspergillus niger*, *Trichoderma reesei* were composting the pulp waste by breaking the sugar molecules in the waste than pulp waste alone (Fig-1) (Ivetić et al., 2014).

Fig -1: Biodegradation of Lignin in the waste products
(Ivetić et al., 2014)

Composting coffee pulp waste is time consuming process. The addition of microorganisms in the composting process of organic compounds reduces the

composting time. Even the microbial consortium is more effective in biodegrading of coffee pulp waste. The organic manure of coffee pulp has been used as a soil amendment for the improvement soil physical, chemical and biological properties with improvement in soil fertility and quality (Table -1)

Table -1: Physico – chemical properties of coffee raw pulp and composted pulp

Parameters	Raw pulp	Composted pulp
Moisture (%)	13.0	57.7
pH (1:10)	5.32	7.89
EC (dS m ⁻¹)	2.24	1.77
Organic C (%)	54.5	35.4
C/N ratio	29.8	11.5
Total N (%)	1.83	2.58
C to N ratio	29.5	12.35

Vermicomposting of coffee pulp

Vermicomposting involves earthworm worms for the decomposition of organic waste materials into vermicast (vermicompost). For this process, 3 types of earthworms are involved epigeic, endogeic and mesogeic. Vermicomposting of coffee pulp requires predigestion with cow dung slurry. The vermicomposting of Coffee pulp using the earthworm *Eisenia foetida* reported by Orozco et al. (1996) and also found that nutrients like nitrates, phosphorus, soluble potassium, calcium, and magnesium present in the coffee pulp based vermicompost was readily utilized up by the plants. Vermicomposting coffee pulp using the exotic *E. eugeniae* and the native earthworm *Perionyx ceylanesis* increased nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium (Raphael et al., 2012).

Conclusions

Composting coffee pulp is vital to convert toxic compounds into harmless products. Microbial agents and earthworms can decompose by-products of coffee like pulp to get nutrient rich organic manure. The co-composting (Widjaja *et al.*, 2017), like the combination of Coffee pulp and other organic residues like leaf litter, fruit and vegetable wastes, can enhance the compost heap temperature, aeration, moisture content and chemical composition of the organic waste materials through the process of decomposition. The organic manure from coffee pulp can be utilized after three months of production to increase the yield of agriculture and horticulture crops. Many studies indicated that the 10: 90 coffee pulp and top soil ratios are suitable for producing seedlings in controlled conditions. However, organic manure from coffee pulp is the viable alternative for commercial growing media for producing vegetable and fruit seedlings in the nursery.

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